

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

GDP per Energy Use at the Global Level

Between 2013 and 2022, the average increase for the countries analyzed was 3.91%.

The variable "GDP/unit of energy use" measures the economic efficiency of a country or region's energy use. In other words, it represents the economic value generated per unit of energy consumed. This metric is calculated as the ratio of GDP to total energy consumption. The formula to calculate "GDP/unit of energy use" is: $\text{GDP per unit of energy use} = \text{GDP} / \text{Energy Consumption}$. Where: GDP is the total value of all final goods and services produced within a country in a given period, usually expressed in US dollars or another local currency; Energy Consumption is the total amount of energy used, expressed in units such as Joules, Terajoules, or equivalents in tons of oil (toe). This indicator is useful for assessing how efficiently an economy uses energy to produce economic value. A higher "GDP/unit of energy use" value indicates greater energy efficiency, as more economic value is produced per unit of energy consumed.

GDP per Energy Use at the Global Level in 2022. In 2022, the "GDP per unit of energy use" index showed significant variation among countries worldwide, reflecting different economic efficiencies in energy use. Ireland topped the rankings with an impressive value of 100, closely followed by Hong Kong SAR, China, with a value of 99.9. These countries demonstrated an extraordinary ability to generate economic value for each unit of energy consumed, positioning themselves well above the global average. This result can be attributed to a combination of advanced technologies, efficient infrastructure, and an economy based on high knowledge intensity and low energy consumption sectors. In sharp contrast, countries like Yemen (86.4), Malta (83.5), and Switzerland (73.7) show high values, although not comparable to the leaders. Switzerland, for instance, despite its high energy efficiency and progressive environmental policies, is at a lower level than Ireland and Hong Kong but remains among the top countries globally. This highlights how even advanced economies can significantly vary in their energy efficiencies. Interestingly, countries like Panama (72.2) and Sri Lanka (67.8), despite being less developed economies compared to the leaders, achieve high values of GDP per unit of energy used. This suggests that even in resource-limited contexts, prudent energy management can lead to notable efficiencies. In these cases, the adoption of sustainable practices and investment in renewable energies may have played a key role. Other European countries such as Denmark (57.3), the UK (48.5), and Germany (39.8) show strong performance in terms of energy efficiency, reflecting advanced energy policies and a long history of investment in clean and renewable technologies. However, it is interesting to note that countries like Italy (43.5) and Spain (41.2) are lower in the rankings, indicating that there is still room for improvement even among advanced economies in Southern Europe. In the context of Latin America, countries like Costa Rica (49.3) and Colombia (47.5) stand out for their high energy efficiencies. Costa Rica, in particular, is

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

known for its commitment to sustainability and the use of renewable energies, which is reflected in its high GDP per unit of energy used. On the other hand, larger countries like Brazil (26.6) and Argentina (26.4) show significantly lower values, suggesting that economies of scale do not always translate into greater energy efficiency. Asia presents a varied picture, with Bangladesh (48.6) and Turkey (45.8) well-positioned in the rankings, while countries like China (15.5) and India (25.4) show lower values. This may reflect the different stages of economic and industrial development and the energy strategies adopted by each country. China, with its vast industrial production, has a high energy demand that does not always translate into an equally high economic output per unit of energy. In the US, the value of 24.2 indicates that despite the abundant resources and advanced technologies, energy efficiency can still be improved. This is particularly relevant in light of climate commitments and strategies to reduce carbon emissions. At the bottom of the rankings are countries like Iceland (3.4), Mozambique (5.1), and Zimbabwe (4.5). These low values can be attributed to less developed economies, inefficient energy infrastructures, and a reliance on traditional energy resources. Iceland, in particular, represents an anomaly since, despite its advanced economy and use of renewable energies, the low value may reflect specific economic dynamics and the nature of its energy production.

GDP per Energy Use at the Global Level between 2013 and 2022. The analysis of GDP per unit of energy used globally from 2013 to 2022 reveals significant variations in energy efficiency among different countries. This indicator is crucial for understanding how nations manage their energy in relation to economic production, highlighting differences in energy policies, infrastructure, and the adoption of sustainable technologies. Among the countries that showed significant improvements, Ghana recorded an increase of 152.69% in its GDP per unit of energy used, rising from 16.7 in 2013 to 42.2 in 2022. This impressive increase suggests that Ghana has implemented effective energy efficiency strategies, possibly through investments in renewable energies and improvements in energy infrastructure. Similarly, Côte d'Ivoire saw an increase of 143.71%, while Yemen registered an increase of 138.02%, despite the political and socio-economic challenges these countries have faced in recent years. These data indicate that, despite difficulties, there have been significant strides in improving energy efficiency, perhaps through targeted government policies and international cooperation. Indonesia and Ireland are other examples of countries that have significantly improved their energy efficiency. Indonesia saw an increase of 88.27%, while Ireland improved by 80.18%. For Ireland, this increase is particularly significant given that it already had a relatively high index of 55.5 in 2013, rising to 100 in 2022. This progress can be attributed to advanced energy policies, a strong focus on renewable energies, and a growing tech economy that tends to use energy more efficiently. Malta and Sri Lanka also showed substantial improvements, with increases of 59.96% and 53.74%, respectively. These progressions may reflect local initiatives aimed at improving energy efficiency, such as adopting green technologies and improvements in energy distribution networks. Other countries that have made significant progress include Bangladesh, Uzbekistan, and Romania, each with increases over 40%. However, not all countries have seen improvements. Hong Kong recorded a slight decline of 0.1%, although it still maintains a very high index close to 100. This suggests that, despite the decline, Hong Kong continues to be one of the world leaders in energy efficiency. Conversely, some countries have seen more significant decreases. Iceland, for example, recorded a 53.42% decline, from 7.3 to 3.4. This decrease may reflect economic challenges and changes in the country's energy production dynamics. Iran saw an even more pronounced decline of 56.25%, which could be due to economic sanctions and limitations in access to advanced technologies. Countries like Canada and Kuwait recorded reductions of 43.4% and 41.51%, respectively. This might indicate an excessive reliance on non-renewable energy resources and inefficiencies in energy infrastructure. Similarly, Brunei saw a decline of 40.73%, suggesting

significant changes in its economic structure and energy practices. Another interesting case is the US, which saw a 10.04% decline, from 26.9 to 24.2. Despite the abundant resources and advanced technologies, US energy efficiency has not significantly improved, highlighting the need for stricter policies and investments in clean technologies. Similarly, European countries such as Germany, France, and Italy saw decreases of 5.01%, 5.1%, and 4.81%, respectively, suggesting that, despite advanced energy policies, there are still significant challenges to improving energy efficiency. Finally, countries at the bottom of the rankings, such as Mozambique and Zimbabwe, which saw declines of 32.89% and 26.81%, face severe economic and infrastructural challenges that prevent significant improvements in energy efficiency. These countries require international support and investments to develop more efficient and sustainable energy infrastructures.

Conclusions. The global value of GDP per energy use grew from 2013 to 2022, with the average for the analyzed countries increasing from 29.69 units to 30.85 units, a 3.91% increase. However, some countries saw their GDP per energy use grow above the period average, such as Ghana with +152.69%, Côte d'Ivoire with +143.71%, Yemen with +138.02%, Indonesia with +88.27%, and Ireland with +80.18%. There are also countries where the GDP per energy use value significantly decreased, such as Brunei Darussalam with -40.73%, Canada with -43.4%, Iceland with -53.42%, and Iran with -56.25%. It should be considered that the growth of GDP per energy use is a very positive element as it highlights the increase in energy efficiency. However, if we look at the data, we can notice that many Western countries between 2013 and 2022 saw this indicator's value decrease, indicating a reduction in energy efficiency contrary to the much-vaunted energy policies against climate change.

Source: Global Innovation Index, https://www.wipo.int/global_innovation_index/en/

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Leogrande, A. (2024). Companies with at least 10 Employees Selling Online across the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4785815*.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Regular Internet Users Across the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4782193*.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Cultural and Creative Employment Across Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN*.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4772381*.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Propensity for Patenting in the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4771132*.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4771131*.

Resta, E., Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3,), 1-15.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Costantiello, A., Leogrande, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The corporate innovation in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3964043*.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-friendly environment in europe. *Available at SSRN 3933553*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The finance-innovation nexus in Europe. *IJISSET-International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, 7(12).

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Impact of Venture Capital Expenditures on Innovation in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3930697*.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., De Cristoforo, G., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Sales Growth Nexus in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3933407*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A.(2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3983218*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. Available at SSRN 4010098.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Matarrese, M. (2022). Innovative SMEs Collaborating with Others in Europe. Available at SSRN 4103840.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Marketing and Organizational Innovations in Europe. Available at SSRN 4186167.

Angelo, L., Laureti, L., & Alberto, C. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. Available at SSRN 4209643.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Role of Non-R&D Expenditures in Promoting Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 4215981.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The opportunity driven entrepreneurship in the context of innovation systems in Europe in the period 2010-2019. Available at SSRN 4229027.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The impact of patent applications on technological innovation in European countries. Available at SSRN 4275264.

Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3), 1-22.

Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Opportunity Driven Entrepreneurship in the Context of Innovation Systems in Europe in the Period 2010-2019. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP*, 28(3), 1-13.